

AI/HPC Cluster Design

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Agenda

- **Introduction to AI/HPC Clusters**
- **Cluster Architecture Overview**
- **Compute**
- **Networking**
- **Software Stack**

Introduction to AI/HPC Clusters

- Compute: Consisting of CPU and GPU nodes.
- Storage: High-performance storage solutions for persisting datasets and trained models.
- Networking: Multiple networks for different types of traffic.
- Data Center: Data center floor planning, power distribution, and cooling.
- Software Stack: Orchestration, scheduling, and management tools for lifecycles management.

Cluster Architecture Overview

To effectively design an AI/HPC cluster, it's crucial to first understand the primary workload use cases.

- **Scientific Computations**

It requires a balance of high **CPU core** counts and significant **memory** per node. Inter-node communication is critical for parallel processing (using MPI). Networking focus is on **low-latency** for these tightly coupled computations.

- **Large-Scale Distributed Training**

It involves training complex AI/ML models on **massive datasets** across multiple nodes. Heavily relies on **GPUs** for parallel computation. Requires very **high-bandwidth and low-latency** interconnects (e.g., **InfiniBand with RDMA**) for efficient gradient sharing and parameter updates between nodes (using techniques such as Pytorch DDP).

Cluster Architecture Overview

- **Fine-Tuning Workloads**

It involves taking a **pre-trained AI/ML model** and further training it on a smaller, specific dataset to specialize the model on a certain task. It requires **fewer GPUs** in compare to full-scale distributed training. Networking requirements might be less stringent than large-scale distributed training but still benefit from high bandwidth for data loading.

- **Inference Workloads (Production AI Clusters)**

Focuses on deploying trained AI/ML models to make predictions on new data. Can be **latency-sensitive**, requiring fast processing and low network latency for serving predictions. Networking needs to be robust for handling incoming requests and delivering predictions efficiently.

Compute

GPU Key Performance Metrics:

GPU Memory:

More memory allows for larger datasets or more complex models to be loaded directly on the GPU.

FLOPs per Precision:

FLOPs (Floating-Point Operations Per Second) quantify the raw computational throughput of a GPU. They are specified for different data precisions, such as **FP64 (double precision)**, **FP32 (single precision)**, **FP16**, or even **FP8**. Lower-precision operations generally allow higher throughput, which is particularly beneficial for AI and deep learning workloads.

Memory Bandwidth and Memory Type:

This metric (typically in terabytes per second, **TB/s**) measures how fast data can be moved between the GPU memory and its processors. **HBM3** memories provide higher speeds than **HBM2**.

Compute

GPU Key Performance Metrics:

GPU Model	GPU Memory	Memory Type	Memory Bandwidth	FP64 Performance	FP32 Performance
NVIDIA H100	80 GB	HBM3	~3.35 TB/s	34 TFLOPS	67 TFLOPS
NVIDIA H200	141 GB	HBM3e	~4.8 TB/s	34 TFLOPS	67 TFLOPS
AMD MI300X	192 GB	HBM3	~5.3 TB/s	81.7 TFLOPS	163.4 TFLOPS

Compute

Calculating Number of GPUs and Nodes for Training a Model:

This is an example for a **1.8 trillion parameter model**, assuming each parameter is stored in FP16 (2 bytes per parameter), to support gradients and activations you need about **3×** the raw parameter memory.

Step	Calculation	Result
Raw parameter memory	$1.8e12 \times 2 \text{ bytes}$	3600 GB
Total memory (with gradients/outputs)	$3600 \text{ GB} \times 3$	10,800 GB
GPUs required (80 GB each)	$10,800 \text{ GB} \div 80 \text{ GB}$	135 GPUs
Nodes required (8 GPUs per node)	$135 \text{ GPUs} \div 8$	17 nodes

Networking

Topology:

Two common topology that are used are Rail and Fat-tree with leaf and spine back bone architecture. Example Diagram for a **32 Node 2-Tier Fat Tree** Topology [(AMD Instinct™ MI300 Series Cluster Reference Architecture Guide, 2025)]:

Networking

Example Diagram for a **32 Node 2-Tier Rail** Topology [(AMD Instinct™ MI300 Series Cluster Reference Architecture Guide, 2025)]:

Networking

Network Configurations:

BGP: In spine-and-leaf architectures, BGP is used as the **underlay routing protocol** due to its scalability and support for complex topologies. It enables efficient route distribution and policy enforcement across the network.

EVPN: EVPN is an **extension of BGP** that provides a scalable and efficient solution that allows for the advertisement of **MAC and IP addresses**. In a VXLAN-based spine-and-leaf architecture, EVPN serves as the control plane, facilitating efficient traffic forwarding.

VXLAN: VXLAN is a network virtualization technology that **encapsulates Layer 2 frames within Layer 3 packets**, allowing for the creation of a virtualized Layer 2 overlay across a Layer 3 infrastructure [The history of network switching. Silvano Gai's Blog. <https://silvanogai.github.io/posts/history/>].

Networking

ECMP: ECMP is a routing strategy that allows multiple paths to be utilized simultaneously for forwarding packets to a destination. In spine-and-leaf architectures, ECMP enables **load balancing** across multiple spine switches, enhancing network bandwidth and redundancy.

Non-Blocking Architecture: A non-blocking architecture ensures that the network can handle the maximum expected traffic without bottlenecks. In spine-and-leaf designs, this is achieved by ensuring that the **number of uplinks (connections from leaf to spine switches) matches the number of downlinks (connections from leaf switches to end nodes)**. This parity ensures that each leaf switch has sufficient bandwidth to handle traffic to and from its connected devices without oversubscription.

48 Ports Leaf Switch

Networking

RDMA: RDMA (Remote Direct Memory Access) is a technology that allows one computer to directly access the memory of another computer without involving the remote CPU. This approach **minimizes latency and reduces CPU overhead** by offloading data transfer tasks to the network interface card (NIC). RDMA should be enabled and supported end to end from application, OS, NIC to the network switches. **PFC (priority flow control) and congestion control (DCQCN)** need to be supported and configured on both NIC and switches.

Networking

Network Isolation:

There are several key reasons that we should have separate physical networks for compute, storage, in-band and out-of-band traffics including Performance optimization, traffic isolation and reduce contention, enhanced security, simplified troubleshooting and maintenance, resiliency and reliability.

Backend Network:

Dedicated for high-speed communication between **compute** nodes (InfiniBand or high-speed Ethernet).

Frontend Networks:

Storage Network: For communication between compute nodes and storage systems (e.g., Ethernet, InfiniBand).

In-band Network: For any infrastructure and observability traffics.

Out-of-band Management Network: For accessing and managing the hardware components (e.g., IPMI, iDRAC).

Networking

Cable Management:

In a leaf-spine topology where a high number of **inter-switch cables** can create significant complexity, proper cable management becomes essential. Here are several strategies to streamline and manage the cabling effectively:

- **Adopt Modular Chassis or Director Switches:** Using director switches or modular chassis with an **integrated backplane** eliminates the need for many external cables. These devices can scale as your network grows, keeping cable density in check while still providing high port counts and redundancy.
- **Implement Structured Cabling and Patch Panels:** Terminate cables in patch panels to consolidate and organize connections. This provides a central point for testing, troubleshooting, and future upgrades. Use cable trays, raceways, and other cable management accessories to physically organize and route cables.

Software Stack

Machine Learning Model Life Cycle Management Tools:

Orchestration : Kubernetes, Slurm, MLFlow, Kubeflow, AzureML

Observability Stack: Prometheus, Loki, Tempo, Grafana

Libraries: Pytorch, Tensorflow, etc.

Thank you

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